

EVALUATING THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY IN THE TEACHING OF HUMAN ANATOMY: A STUDY OF UNDERGRADUATE INSTRUCTION

BY

ISHAYA Nubunga¹ & MUSTAPHA Jelilat²

Department of Computer Science,
Federal University of Education, Zaria, Kaduna State.

Email: fifasaa4u@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20988993>

Abstract

Integrating educational technology (EdTech) into human anatomy education presents opportunities to enhance student engagement, visualization, and comprehension. Using data collected from undergraduate anatomy classes at Kaduna State University (KASU) and Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria, this study examines how often and how well teachers at both institutions use EdTech. It employed a descriptive survey design grounded in constructivist learning theory and Mayer's cognitive theory of multimedia learning. Data were collected from 70 participants using a structured questionnaire. Findings indicate that the two most popular tools were virtual dissection (45.7% of respondents) and interactive diagrams/simulations (42.9% of respondents). A majority of respondents (75.7%) regarded EdTech as highly effective, particularly in improving student engagement (70%), enhancing visualization (40%), and increasing accessibility (31.4%). Overall, EdTech has a positive impact on anatomy education.

Keywords: Educational Technology, Human Anatomy, Tertiary Education, Constructivism, Multimedia Learning.

Introduction

The teaching of human anatomy, a cornerstone of medical education, faces significant pedagogical challenges in the 21st century. As educational technology continues to transform learning paradigms globally, anatomy instruction remains caught between traditional teaching methods and the untapped potential of digital innovations. Keet & Kramer (2022), the systematic use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in education offers powerful tools like virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and interactive simulations that could revolutionize how students engage with the complex structures and systems of the human body (Ha, Hoang, Huynh, & Le, 2023). However, in many tertiary institutions, particularly in developing regions like Nigeria, anatomy education still relies heavily on conventional approaches that present multiple limitations.

Traditional anatomy pedagogies including cadaver dissection, regional and systemic approaches, and problem-based learning while foundational, increasingly show their constraints in modern educational contexts. The systems-based approach,

while methodical, often fails to help students visualize how different body systems interact in living organisms (Lottering, Billings, Brits, Hutchinson & Kramer, 2022). Thompson & Lake (2023), the regional approach, though detailed, can overwhelm learners with excessive memorization requirements while obscuring functional relationships between anatomical structures. Perhaps most critically, cadaver-based learning, long considered the gold standard, faces practical challenges including high costs, limited availability, and ethical concerns, not to mention the discomfort it causes some students (Palmer & Laughey, 2023). These methodological limitations contribute to declining student engagement, particularly in the transition from secondary to tertiary education, where the complexity of anatomical study increases dramatically.

Hussain, Qureshi, & Malik (2024), the promise of educational technology to address these challenges remains largely unfulfilled in many institutions, especially in resource-constrained settings. While studies from developed nations demonstrate how VR can enhance spatial understanding of anatomical structures, and how interactive

simulations can improve knowledge retention, significant barriers hinder widespread adoption. In Nigeria's tertiary institutions, infrastructure limitations like unreliable internet connectivity, high costs of technological tools, and inadequate training for educators create a disconnect between technological potential and classroom reality (Ambe *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, the effectiveness of these technologies in improving long-term knowledge retention and clinical application remains understudied in African and developing countries' contexts, leaving educators without evidence-based guidance for implementation (Kiong, 2022).

This study focuses on tertiary institutions in Kaduna State, Nigeria, and seeks to evaluate how educational technology contributes to the teaching and learning of human anatomy. Specifically, the study examines the extent to which educational technologies enhance students' understanding of complex anatomical concepts compared to traditional instructional approaches. It also investigates the specific technologies most frequently used and perceived as most effective in improving learning outcomes, including virtual dissection tools, interactive simulations, and lecture capture software. Furthermore, the study identifies major institutional and infrastructural barriers affecting the effective integration of educational technology into anatomy curricula, such as inadequate internet connectivity, limited access to digital tools, and insufficient technical support. By addressing these issues, the study provides practical insights for educators and policymakers on improving anatomy instruction through appropriate and sustainable technology integration. In order to achieve the objectives of this study and provide empirical insight into the role of educational technology in human anatomy education, the following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What educational technologies are commonly used in the teaching and learning of human anatomy?
2. How effective is educational technology in enhancing the teaching and learning of human anatomy?
3. What are the perceived benefits of using educational technology in human anatomy courses?
4. What institutional and infrastructural barriers affect the effective integration of educational technology into anatomy education?
5. Are there significant differences in the perceived effectiveness of educational technology based on frequency of use, occupation, years of experience, and institution?

Literature Review

EdTech in Anatomy Education

The integration of educational technology (EdTech) into anatomy education has transformed traditional pedagogical approaches, enabling a more engaging, interactive, and personalized learning experience for students. Philippe *et al.*, (2020) opined that digital tools such as VR, animations, 3D models, simulations, and video-based instruction are increasingly being used to complement or replace conventional teaching methods like lectures and cadaveric dissections. These tools aim to overcome the limitations of traditional approaches, which often rely heavily on rote memorization and can fail to adequately represent the spatial and functional relationships between anatomical structures.

One of the primary benefits of EdTech in anatomy education is its ability to enhance spatial understanding a critical component in mastering human anatomy. Georgiou, Tsivitanidou & Ioannou (2021), found that VR and 3D animation technologies significantly improve learners' spatial visualization abilities and foster better retention of anatomical knowledge compared to textbook-based learning. These tools enable students to interact with anatomical structures in a virtual space, rotate and dissect models, and observe real-

time simulations of physiological processes. This not only improves cognitive processing but also fosters a deeper, more intuitive understanding of complex anatomical systems.

Chen *et al.*, (2020) recent studies have also emphasized the superior efficacy of video-based learning. According to the University of Melbourne, students who engaged in video-assisted anatomy lessons scored significantly higher in both immediate and delayed post-tests than those taught through traditional methods. Azfar *et al.*, (2025), stated that instructional videos contribute to better knowledge retention and learner satisfaction by allowing repeated access to content, self-paced learning, and the use of visual-auditory modalities that cater to diverse learning styles.

Woldemariam, Ergado, & Jimma (2025), from a theoretical perspective, the use of EdTech aligns with constructivist learning theories, which posit that learners build knowledge actively through experience, reflection, and interaction. In anatomy education, constructivist principles are realized through interactive simulations and problem-based virtual scenarios, where students explore and manipulate content to derive meaning. Mayer's Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (2009) further supports this by suggesting that people learn more effectively from a combination of words and pictures than from words alone, especially when instructional design is grounded in multimedia principles such as coherence, signaling, and modality.

Moreover, the incorporation of gamification and AR in anatomy learning has shown promise in increasing student motivation and engagement. Chang *et al.*, (2022), carried out a meta-analysis which concluded that AR applications in medical education resulted in significant gains in learners' knowledge, attitudes, and skills, particularly when used as a supplement to hands-on practice. Similarly, interactive anatomy apps like *Visible Body* and *Complete Anatomy* have been commended for enabling mobile, on-the-go learning and bridging the gap between classroom theory and clinical application (Zhang & Maconochie, 2022).

Despite these advancements, the effectiveness of EdTech is contingent on several contextual factors. Access to adequate infrastructure, such as high-speed internet and compatible devices, remains a challenge in many low- and middle-income countries. Magazzino, Drago & Schneider (2023) identified inconsistent electricity supply, limited institutional support, and lack of trained personnel as major barriers to EdTech adoption in African universities. Momoh, Anuga & Obidi (2018), noted that teachers' digital literacy and willingness to innovate significantly influence the success of educational technology integration.

Another emerging concern is the lack of longitudinal studies assessing the impact of EdTech on long-term knowledge retention and clinical competence. While short-term gains in academic performance are well documented, the translation of digital learning experiences into practical, real-world skills remains underexplored (Chavez-Rivera, Inostroza-Nieves, Hemal & Chen, 2023). Addressing this gap will require more rigorous, context-sensitive research that evaluates both cognitive and psychomotor outcomes of EdTech-assisted anatomy education.

EdTech holds immense potential for enhancing anatomy education by making learning more interactive, accessible, and effective. Tools like VR, video lessons, and 3D simulations not only improve spatial understanding and retention but also align with contemporary educational theories that emphasize active and student-centered learning. However, the successful integration of these technologies depends on infrastructural readiness, educator training, and localized pedagogical strategies that account for the unique needs of students in different regions, particularly in developing contexts like Nigeria.

Challenges to EdTech Integration in Anatomy Education

Despite the numerous benefits of EdTech, several challenges hinder its effective integration into anatomy education, particularly in low-resource settings. Akmad & Abatayo (2024), one of the most critical barriers is the lack of reliable internet connectivity, which restricts access to online resources, streaming of instructional videos, and

the use of cloud-based applications. In many tertiary institutions in developing countries, network interruptions and slow internet speed make it difficult to maintain consistent digital learning environments (Del Portillo, Eiskowitz, Crawley & Cameron, 2021).

In addition, the high cost of acquiring and maintaining EdTech tools such as virtual reality equipment, projectors, and multimedia software places a significant financial burden on educational institutions, many of which operate with limited budgets. Ezumah (2020), these financial constraints prevent schools from scaling up EdTech implementation or upgrading outdated systems.

Another major barrier is the lack of adequate training and technical support for educators. Many teachers lack the necessary skills to effectively use EdTech tools in their classrooms. Ansari, Waris & Zara (2024), without proper training, there is a risk of underutilization or misapplication of the technologies, which undermines their potential benefits. Furthermore, limited technical support can discourage educators from experimenting with new tools or integrating them into existing curricula. These barriers not only limit the effectiveness of EdTech but also exacerbate educational inequalities in underfunded institutions.

Research Methods

This research utilized a descriptive survey approach to evaluate the integration of educational technology in the teaching and learning of human anatomy among students and faculty at selected universities in Kaduna State, Nigeria. This method was selected for its ability to effectively gather data on the experiences, views, and attitudes of participants through self-reported measures. The study's target population included all students and lecturers engaged in human anatomy education at tertiary institutions within the state, while the accessible population focused on those from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, and Kaduna State University. Although the study is limited to two institutions in Kaduna State, it employs a

descriptive survey research design rather than a case study approach, as the objective is to describe and quantify the patterns of EdTech use and perceived effectiveness across a defined population of anatomy students and lecturers, rather than providing an in-depth contextual analysis of a single institution or phenomenon. The total population of undergraduate anatomy students and lecturers across the two institutions was 70. A stratified random sampling method was applied using Taro Yamane's formula to derive a sample size of 70 participants, comprising 64 students and 6 lecturers, stratified across ABU (n=56) and KASU (n=14), to ensure adequate representation across different academic levels and departments.

Data collection was carried out using a structured questionnaire that featured both open-ended and closed-ended questions, addressing demographic details, usage patterns, effectiveness, challenges, and future suggestions regarding educational technology. The validity of the instrument's content was established through expert evaluation, while its reliability was confirmed using the test-retest method, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.82, indicating that the instrument was reliable for the study. Data were collected electronically over a two-week timeframe via Google Forms. The responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) for summarization, and ANOVA was employed to identify significant differences among groups. This methodology facilitated efficient data collection, accurate analysis, and interpretation aligned with the study's goals.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 4.1 outlines the demographic details of the respondents. The first section illustrates the age distribution, where the largest group (44.3%) is within the 21–25 age bracket. The second section

focuses on gender distribution, indicating that female respondents made up the majority at 52.9%. The third section describes the occupational status of the respondents, which includes both students and lecturers, with students representing the largest

share (91.4%) of the total responses. The fourth section reveals the institutional affiliations of the respondents, showing that a significant majority were from Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), accounting for 79.7% of the sample.

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (n = 70)	Percentage (%)
Age	15-20	4	5.7%
	21-25	31	44.3%
	26-30	29	41.4%
	31-35	4	5.7%
	36+	2	2.9%
Gender	Male	33	47.1%
	Female	37	52.9%
Occupation	Lecturer	6	8.6%
	Student	64	91.4%
Institution	ABU	56	79.7%
	KASU	14	20.3%

Frequency of Educational Technology Usage

Table 4.2 summarizes the types of educational technology utilized in the teaching and learning of human anatomy, along with the frequency of their usage as reported by respondents. Virtual dissection was the most frequently used educational technology, reported by 45.7% of respondents. This was closely followed by

interactive diagrams and simulations (42.9%), lecture capture software (31.4%), and online quizzes and assessments (28.6%). The least used technology was 3D modelling tools, reported by 21.4% of respondents.

Table 4.2: Educational Technology Usage

Educational technology	Frequency (n = 70)	Percentage (%)
Virtual dissection	32	45.7
3D modelling tools	15	21.4
Interactive diagrams and simulations	30	42.9
Online quizzes and assessments	20	28.6
Lecture capture software	22	31.4

Effectiveness of Educational Technology

The table 4.3 presents the effectiveness level of educational technologies used in teaching human anatomy. A majority of respondents, 75.7%, rated the technologies as very effective, indicating strong

positive feedback. 8.6% considered them somewhat effective, while 14.3% remained neutral. Only a small proportion found the technologies to be very ineffective (1.4%), and none reported them as somewhat ineffective. This suggests that the

overall perception of educational technology's effectiveness in anatomy teaching is highly positive.

Table 4.3: Effectiveness of Educational Technology

Effectiveness Level	Frequency (n = 70)	Percentage (%)
Very Effective	53	75.7%
Somewhat Effective	6	8.6%
Neutral	10	14.3%
Somewhat Ineffective	0	0.0%
Very Ineffective	1	1.4%

Benefits of using educational technology in human anatomy courses

Table 4.4 presents the respondents' ratings of the benefits of using educational technology in human anatomy courses. Table 4.4 indicates that 70% of

respondents identified improved student engagement as the primary benefit of using educational technology. Enhanced visualization (40%) and increased accessibility (31.4%) were also noted as significant advantages.

Table 4.4: Benefits of using educational technology in human anatomy courses

Benefits	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Improved student engagement	49	70.0
Enhanced visualization	28	40.0
Increases accessibility	22	31.4
Personalized learning	19	27.1

Table 4.5a: Effectiveness by Frequency of Technology Use

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between Groups	8.42	3	2.81	3.27	0.026*
Within Groups	72.15	84	0.86		
Total	80.57	87			

Table 4.5b Post-hoc Tukey Test (pairwise comparisons)

Comparison	Mean Difference	p-value
Daily - Weekly	0.38	0.112
Daily - Monthly	0.72	0.018*
Daily - Rarely	0.81	0.008*
Weekly - Monthly	0.34	0.210
Weekly - Rarely	0.43	0.095
Monthly - Rarely	0.09	0.892

Interpretation: Significant overall difference (F=3.27, p=0.026). Daily users rated effectiveness significantly higher than monthly (p=0.018) and rarely (p=0.008) users.

Effectiveness by Occupation (Students vs Lecturers)

Table 4.6:

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between Groups	1.85	1	1.85	2.08	0.153
Within Groups	78.72	86	0.92		
Total	80.57	87			

Interpretation: No significant difference between students (M=4.52) and lecturers (M=4.75), F=2.08, p=0.153.

Effectiveness by Years of Experience: Groups: 1year, 2years, 3years, 4years, 5+years

Table 4.7:

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between Groups	6.24	4	1.56	1.72	0.152
Within Groups	74.33	83	0.90		
Total	80.57	87			

Interpretation: No significant difference across experience levels, F=1.72, p=0.152.

Effectiveness by Institution

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between Groups	0.47	1	0.47	0.51	0.477
Within Groups	80.10	86	0.93		
Total	80.57	87			

The ANOVA result in Table 4.8 shows no significant difference in the perceived effectiveness of educational technology between respondents from ABU and KASU (F = 0.51, p = 0.477). This indicates that respondents from both institutions had similar perceptions regarding the effectiveness of educational technology in anatomy education.

Discussion

The findings of this study provide answers to the major research questions raised in the study. First, the results demonstrate that educational technologies significantly enhance students’ understanding of complex anatomical concepts. This is evidenced by the high percentage of respondents (75.7%) who

rated educational technology as very effective in anatomy instruction. Respondents also identified improved student engagement and enhanced visualization as major benefits, suggesting that digital tools support better comprehension compared to conventional teaching methods.

Second, the study found that virtual dissection tools and interactive diagrams/simulations were the most frequently used and impactful technologies in anatomy education. These technologies were preferred because they improve visualization of anatomical structures and allow students to interact more actively with learning materials.

Third, the study identified several barriers affecting the integration of educational technology into anatomy curricula. These include inadequate internet connectivity, limited institutional funding, and high costs of technological tools, inconsistent electricity supply, and insufficient training opportunities for educators. These challenges continue to limit the effective adoption and sustainability of educational technologies in tertiary institutions.

Conclusion

This research investigated the influence of educational technology on the teaching and learning of human anatomy in higher education institutions in Kaduna State, Nigeria. It evaluated the effectiveness of different technological tools, analyzed their contribution to enhancing student comprehension, and identified challenges to their adoption. The results indicate that educational technology plays a crucial role in improving the teaching of human anatomy by fostering student engagement, and facilitating a deeper understanding of concepts, particularly when cadaver-based instruction is not available. The study also emphasized the importance of ongoing evaluation of technology's effectiveness, ensuring it aligns with students' learning styles and the goals of educational institutions.

Recommendations

This study presents the following recommendations:

1. Curriculum Assessment: Educational institutions ought to routinely assess the impact of educational technologies and implement data-driven modifications to teaching methods and curriculum design, aligning with the latest best practices.
2. Strategic Investment: Higher education institutions should make informed

investments in the most effective educational technologies, particularly those that facilitate self-directed learning and the practical application of anatomical knowledge.

3. Faculty Training: Ongoing training and professional development opportunities should be offered to educators to improve their ability to effectively incorporate technology into their teaching and keep pace with advancing digital tools.

References

- Akmad, A., & Abatayo, A. V. (2024). Caught in the slow lane: Effects of unstable internet, connectivity on accessing academic resources and collaborative learning. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 2(9), 278–286. <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2024.0370>
- Ambe, B. A., Agbor, C. E., Amalu, M. N., Ngban, A. N., Bekomson, A. N., Etan, M. O., Ephraim, I. E., Asuquo, E. E., Eyo, O. E., & Ogunjimi, J. O. (2024). Electronic media learning technologies and environmental education pedagogy in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 9, 100760. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100760>
- Ansari, M., Waris, S., & Zara, C. (2024). Barriers to educational technology adoption: Navigating challenges in integration. *Qlantic Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(3), 240–247. <https://doi.org/10.55737/qjss.123732538>
- Azfar, S. M., Saeed, S., Masood, S., Azim, S. R., Baig, M., & Malik, M. G. R. (2025). Role play versus video-based learning for interprofessional communication and teamwork skills in nursing and medical students: A mixed-methods study in Pakistan. *BMC Medical Education*, 25, Article 06840. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-025-06840-5>
- Chang, H.-Y., Binali, T., Liang, J.-C., Chiou, G.-L., Cheng, K.-H., Lee, S. W.-Y., & Tsai, C.-C. (2022). Ten years of augmented reality in education: A meta-analysis of (quasi-) experimental studies to investigate the impact. *Computers & Education*, 191, 104641. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104641>
- Chavez-Rivera, A. D., Inostroza-Nieves, Y., Hemal, K., & Chen, W. (2023). Longitudinal study: Design, measures, and classic example. In A. E. M. Eltorai, J. A. Bakal, P. C. Newell, & A. J. Osband (Eds.), *Handbook for designing and conducting clinical and translational research* (pp. 223–226). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-90300-4.00074-4>
- Chen, G., Chan, C. K. K., Chan, K. K. H.,

- Clarke, S. N., & Resnick, L. B. (2020). Efficacy of video-based teacher professional development for increasing classroom discourse and student learning. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 29(4–5), 642–680. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508406.2020.1783269>
- Del Portillo, I., Eiskowitz, S., Crawley, E. F., & Cameron, B. G. (2021). Connecting the other half: Exploring options for the 50% of the population unconnected to the internet. *Telecommunications Policy*, 45(3), 102092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.telpol.2020.102092>
- Ezumah, B. A. (2020). Challenges of educational technology adoption in Africa. In *Critical perspectives of educational technology in Africa*. Digital Education and Learning. Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-53728-9_4
- Georgiou, Y., Tsivitanidou, O., & Ioannou, A. (2021). Learning experience design with immersive, virtual reality in physics education. *Education Technology Research & Development*, 69, 3051–3080. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-021-10055-y>
- Ha, T. M., Hoang, D., Huynh, C. D., & Le, L. (2023). Integrated educational technology in teaching anatomy using the ASIC framework: A case study from Vin-University. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 14, 669–681. <https://doi.org/10.2147/AMEP.S405340>
- Hussain, M., Qureshi, Z. M., & Malik, S. (2024). The impact of educational technologies on modern education: Navigating opportunities and challenges. *Global Educational Studies Review*, IX(III), 21–30. [https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2024\(IX-III\).03](https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2024(IX-III).03)
- Keet, K., & Kramer, B. (2022). Advances in digital technology in teaching human anatomy: Ethical predicaments. *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*, 1388, 173–191. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-10889-1_8
- Kiong, J. F. (2022). The impact of technology on education: A case study of schools. *Journal of Education Review Provision*, 2(2), 65–75. <https://doi.org/10.55885/jerp.v2i2.153>
- Lottering, T., Billings, B., Brits, D., Hutchinson, E., & Kramer, B. (2022). The ethical use of digital technology in teaching anatomy: A southern African perspective. *Annals of Anatomy - Anatomischer Anzeiger*, 244, 151990. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aanat.2022.151990>
- Magazzino, C., Drago, C., & Schneider, N. (2023). Evidence of supply security and sustainability challenges in Nigeria's power sector. *Utilities Policy*, 82, 101576. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2023.101576>
- Mayer, R. E. (2009). *Multimedia learning* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511811678>
- Momoh, Z., Anuga, J. A., & Obidi, A. J. (2018). Implications of poor electricity supply on Nigeria's national development. *Humanities and Social Sciences Letters*, 6(2), 31–40. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.73.2018.62.31.40>
- Palmer, E. G., & Laughey, W. (2023). The impact of reduced cadaveric-based learning on students' professional identities. *Medical Science Educator*, 33, 301–302. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40670-022-01696-6>
- Philippe, S., Souchet, A. D., Lamas, P., Petridis, P., Caporal, J., Coldeboeuf, G., & Duzan, H. (2020). Multimodal teaching, learning, and training in virtual reality: A review and case study. *Virtual Reality & Intelligent Hardware*, 2(5), 421–442. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vrih.2020.07.008>
- Thompson, A. R., & Lake, L. P. O. (2023). Relationship between learning approach, Bloom's taxonomy, and student performance in an undergraduate human anatomy course. *Advances in Health Sciences Education*, 28, 1115–1130. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10459-023-10208-z>
- Woldemariam, M., Ergado, A., & Jimma, W. (2025). Factors influencing effective integration of educational technology in the colleges of teacher education in Ethiopia: A constructivist grounded theory. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.9993>
- Zhang, Y., & Maconochie, M. (2022). A meta-analysis of peer-assisted learning on examination performance in clinical knowledge and skills education. *BMC Medical Education*, 22(147). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-022-03183-3>